

Rice varieties showing resistance to RTSV infection.

IRGC acc. no.	Variety ^a	RTSV infection (%)		IRGC acc. no.	Variety ^a	RTSV infection (%)	
		Exp. 1	Exp. 2			Exp. 1	Exp. 2
177	Adday Sel.	0	0	26789	Shalya*	0	0
180	Adday Local Sel.	0	0	26791	Sham Rosh	0	0
4021	Binicol*	0	0	26813	Gogoj	0	0
5999	Pankhari 203*	0	1	27529	Bhoilush*	0	0
7366	PI 184675-2*	0	0	27779	Bara Pashawari 390	0	0
8261	Padi Kasalle	0	8	27781	Bara 413*	0	0
11062	G378	0	0	27787	Basmati Nahan 381	0	3
11751	Habiganj DW 8	0	0	27798	Basmati 1	3	0
12203	ARC6064*	0	0	27799	Basmati 43 A*	0	0
12274	ARC6561	0	0	27800	Basmati 93*	3	0
12310	ARC7007*	0	0	27803	Basmati 107*	0	0
12428	ARC10312	0	3	27804	Basmati 113*	0	0
12437	ARC10343	0	0	27805	Basmati 122*	0	0
14504	IR580 420-1-1-2	0	0	27814	Basmati 208*	0	0
14527	Barah	0	0	27818	Basmati 242	0	0
14649	Gendjah Melati	0	5	27821	Basmati 370 A*	0	0
14703	CPA86805-2*	0	0	27828	Basmati 376*	0	0
15769	Lawangeen*	0	6	27829	Basmati 377	0	0
16680	Utri Merah	3	0	27830	Basmati 388	0	0
16684	Utri Rajapan	0	0	27832	Basmati 405	0	3
19680	ARC10963	0	0	27833	Basmati 406	0	0
20600	ARC7321	0	0	27835	Basmati 427*	0	0
21164	ARC10980	0	0	27836	Basmati 433	0	0
21310	ARC11315	0	3	27856	Begumi 302	0	0
21337	ARC11346	5	3	27869	Chahora 144	0	0
21342	ARC11353	0	3	27870	Chahora 148	0	0
21473	ARC11554*	0	0	27872	Chahora 292	0	0
21474	ARC11555	0	0	27873	Chahora 382	0	0
21745	ARC11920	0	0	27916	Dhanlu 254	5	5
21958	ARC12170	0	0	27943	Hansraj 54*	0	0
22176	ARC12596	9	0	27946	Hansraj 62	0	0
22199	ARC12620	0	3	27947	Hansraj 189	0	0
22215	ARC12636	0	0	27948	Hansraj 197	0	3
22307	ARC12746	0	0	27951	Hansraj 365 A	0	0
22331	ARC12778	0	0	28102	P590	0	0
26253	Nep Bap	0	0	28320	Toga 286 A*	0	0
26295	Bale Betor*	0	0	28341	9*	0	0
26316	Birpala*	0	3	28450	361*	0	0
26410	Pala Bhir	0	3	28522	Gundrikbhog	6	0
26418	Shada Muta*	0	0	28867	AUS4	0	0
26495	Konek Chul	0	0	31746	Bish Katari*	5	0
26527	Shuli 2	0	0	36731	Firro E (1)	0	0
26560	Bharat*	0	0	37215	Matichakma	0	0
26582	Buchi 2	0	0	37337	Urman Sardar	0	2
26622	Gia Dhan*	0	5	37430	Ghigos	0	0
26633	Gurdoi*	0	5	37482	Kanakchul	0	0
26663	Kaisha Binni*	3	0	37488	Kashiabinni*	0	0
26703	Kurki*	0	0	37491	Katijan*	0	0
26715	Lao Bhug*	0	0	37761	Maliabhangor 1096	0	0
26784	Sakor	0	5	49996	Ovarkondoh	0	0

*Asterisk indicates the possibility that apparent RTSV resistance may be due to vector resistance.

Pest resistance— insects

Screening entries in the International Rice Whitebacked Planthopper Nursery (IRWBPHN) 1991 for resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in Ludhiana, India

J. Singh, G. S. Sidhu, K. K. Shukla, and D. R. Sharma, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

Sixty-seven entries, including two of TN1, of the ninth IRWBPHN were screened for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) under

Promising entries with resistance to WBPH in IRWBPHN 1991. Ludhiana, India, 1991.

Entries scoring 3.0

IR12665-7-1-3-6
IR15527-21-2-3
IR31429-14-2-3
IR31785-58-1-2-3-3
IR2035-117-3
IR43342-10-1-1-3-3

Entries scoring 3.7

ARC6248 (local check)
Baggi Munji 22
BR4-34-13-5
BR850-9-1-1
B3906 D-14-ST-16-48-3
GH305
IR65

Entries scoring 4.3

IR13475-7-3-2
IR35366-40-3-3-2-2
IR43491-140-1-2-3

Entries scoring 5.0

Bamla Red 310-6
CR94-13
IR28526-44-1-1
IR29429-13-3-B-1-4
IR35293-125-3-2-3
IR35366-28-3-1-2-2
IR35366-62-1-2-2-3
IR39334-31-2-2-2
IR39357-45-3-2-3
IR60
Rami chudi
RP1442-2-2-3-5-1
RP1579-28-54
UPRH193
WC1240

glasshouse conditions with three replications. Local resistant check ARC6248 was included.

We evaluated the entries using the 0-9

scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when susceptible check TN1 died.

Twelve entries were scored as resistant (3.0-3.7), 18 were moderately resistant

(4.3-5.0), 28 susceptible (5.7-7.0), and 7 highly susceptible (7.7-9.0). Promising entries are listed in the table. ■

Screening rice varieties and lines for resistance to yellow stem borer (YSB) based on preference or nonpreference and antibiosis

M. Riaz, M. Ahmed, and A. Butt, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Punjab, Pakistan

We screened 16 varieties and lines for resistance to YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in a cage in 1990. We transplanted five seedlings of each entry with a spacing of 25 cm between plants and 35 cm between varieties. The experimental design was completely randomized. We collected three replications of adult female moths from fields and kept them on Basmati 370 in a separate cage for oviposition. Each tiller was artificially infested 30 d after transplanting with two first-instar larvae that had been collected from the egg masses.

Five tillers with deadhearts from each variety were randomly dissected and larvae removed and weighed at 20 d after infestation.

We studied preference or nonpreference mechanism of resistance by randomly placing all entries in a wooden cage in three replications. Test material was exposed to oviposition by 100 female YSB moths early in the morning. We counted the egg masses laid on varieties and lines after 2 d.

TKM6, Basmati 385, and 4321 had the fewest deadhearts and whiteheads of the test entries (see table). TKM6 and Basmati 385 exhibited the nonpreference and antibiosis mechanism of resistance. 4321 showed preference and antibiosis behavior for YSB. Basmati 370, Basmati 198, and 4439 were susceptible to YSB. Other varieties and lines were moderately resistant to YSB. Resistant varieties exhibited nonpreference and antibiosis mechanism of resistance. ■

Performance of 16 varieties and lines under antibiosis and preference/nonpreference mechanism of resistance.* Punjab, Pakistan, 1990.

Variety or line	Av deadhearts (%)	Av weight of 5 larvae (mg)	Egg mass (av no.)
Basmati 385	15.91 ef	0.187 f	2 de
Basmati 370	44.66 a	0.277 d	6 c
4048	31.07 abcde	0.285 cd	4 cd
Basmati 198	36.73 abcd	0.300 abc	4 cd
6129	40.37 abc	0.310 a	4 c
PK2773-1-2-3	22.98 cdef	0.289 bcd	3 de
1053-2-4	38.22 abcd	0.301 abc	4 cd
4439	37.06 abcd	0.302 ab	9 b
4029-1	26.79 abcdef	0.285 bcd	10 e
4029-2	42.83 ab	0.310 a	4 cd
PK729-15-7	24.66 cdef	0.311 a	4 cd
1053-1-2	28.65 abcdef	0.301 abc	3 de
50189-8-6	25.78 bcdef	0.290 bcd	1 e
4321	17.66 ef	0.240 e	14 a
4048-3	22.19 def	0.302 ab	4 cd
TKM6	11.61 f	0.182 f	10 e
	LSD = 18.07		LSD = 2.58

*In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Changes in brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam

Nguyen Long Chau, Southern Regional Center for Plant Protection (SCPP), Tiengiang Province (Mekong Delta); Nguyen Cong Thuat and Vu Thi Chai, Institute of Plant Protection (IPP), Hanoi, Vietnam

BPH is one of the important insect pests of rice in southern Vietnam. In 1988-91, popular varieties IR36, IR66, IR42, MTL 61 (IR19728), and MTL 58 (IR13240-108-3-2-2)—all of which have the *bph 2* resistance gene—were hopperburned in many areas of the Mekong Delta.

We collected seven BPH field populations from different agroecological areas of the Mekong Delta in 1991 to determine the changes in BPH biotype using the modified bulk seedling test. Check varieties were seeded in 20-cm rows, 5 cm apart, in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes and replicated three times. Test entries were infested 7 d after seeding with seven second- and third-instar nymphs per seedling. We visually rated damage using the *Standard*

evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale when the susceptible check TN1 had died.

All BPH populations studied killed TN1. Mudgo (*Bph 1*) was susceptible to all seven BPH populations. The resistance of ASD7 (*bph 2*) broke down, indicating that BPH biotype 2 had developed a new distinct biotype that was not similar to biotype 3 from IRRI. Rathu Heenati (*Bph 3*) and Ptb 33 (digenic gene) were still resistant to all populations. Babawee (*bph 4*) was moderately susceptible or susceptible to all BPH populations (Table 1 on next page).

BPH virulence in the Mekong Delta is apparently increasing because of natural adaptive selection. Reactions of different populations in various areas were relatively similar. It appears that a new biotype, the "Mekong Delta BPH population," has developed.

To clarify the new biotype reaction, we compared it with biotypes of some Asian rice-growing countries. The new BPH biotype is completely different from those in the Philippines, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, and India (Table 2 on next page). ■